

Bioinformatics-Based ceRNA Network Analysis and miRNA Expression Profiling in Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL) Using Real-Time PCR

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Abstract

Introduction: Leukemia is the most common type of cancer in children, with acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) accounting for 80% of cases. MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are a novel class of regulatory RNAs approximately 22 nucleotides in length. These molecules play critical roles in regulating gene expression and various biological pathways, such as apoptosis, across many human cancers. Depending on the context, miRNAs can act as oncogenes or tumor suppressors and hold potential as biomarkers for cancer diagnosis and prognosis.

Materials and Methods: A competing endogenous RNA (ceRNA) network comprising mRNA, lncRNA, and miRNA associated with ALL was constructed, leading to the selection of a candidate miRNA for experimental validation. The MOLT-4 cell line was used as the cancerous model, and normal cells isolated via PBMC technique served as the control. Total RNA was extracted, cDNA synthesized, and miRNA-21 expression levels were assessed using RT-qPCR.

Results: Analysis of RT-qPCR data demonstrated a significant upregulation of miRNA-21 in the MOLT-4 cell line. A p-value of <0.0001 indicated a strong and significant correlation between miRNA-21 expression and its role in ALL pathogenesis.

Conclusion: Given the critical role of miRNAs in various cancers, they have potential as novel diagnostic markers or non-invasive tools for early cancer detection. This study highlights the regulatory role of miRNA-21 in ALL, suggesting its utility as a potential biomarker in this malignancy.

Keywords: Acute lymphoblastic leukemia, MicroRNA, MOLT-4, qPCR, miRNA-21.

1. Introduction

Acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) is a blood cancer involving uncontrolled growth of lymphoid progenitor cells in the bone marrow and other tissues. It has a bimodal incidence, peaking in early childhood and around age 50 (1).

While children have a high cure rate of nearly 90%, adults fare worse, with cure rates of 40%–60% in younger adults and just 20% in those over 60 (2). The standard treatment for adult B-cell ALL has long been multidrug chemotherapy, achieving complete remission in 80%–90% of cases. However, many patients relapse, and the prognosis for relapsed or refractory ALL remains poor, with less than 10% achieving 5-year survival (3).

Competing endogenous RNAs (ceRNAs) are transcripts that share similar microRNA response elements (MREs), enabling them to compete for the same microRNAs (miRNAs) (4). miRNAs are small non-coding RNAs that regulate gene expression by binding to MREs on target mRNAs, leading to mRNA degradation or inhibition of protein translation (5).

ceRNAs, including mRNAs, circular RNAs, long non-coding RNAs, and pseudogenes, form ceRNA networks that influence biological processes by modulating miRNA activity (6).

Cancer drug resistance, a major challenge in chemotherapy, has been linked to ceRNA crosstalk (7). Recent studies highlight ceRNA dysregulation as a mechanism underlying drug resistance in various cancers and suggest their potential as prognostic biomarkers for predicting chemotherapy response (8). However, experimental validation of computationally predicted ceRNA networks is necessary for their clinical application in cancer therapy.

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the regulatory role of miRNA-21 within the competing endogenous RNA (ceRNA) network in the pathogenesis of acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) and to evaluate its potential as a diagnostic biomarker, contributing to the development of non-invasive methods for early detection and improved understanding of miRNA-mediated mechanisms in leukemia.

This research aims to contribute to the development of non-invasive diagnostic methods and enhance understanding of ceRNA-mediated mechanisms in leukemia.

2. Material and Methods

1. Data Acquisition and Preprocessing

To construct a ceRNA network related to Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL), we retrieved publicly available transcriptomic datasets from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) and The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA). Datasets included microRNA expression profiles from ALL patient samples and healthy controls.

2. Construction of the ceRNA Network

A ceRNA network was constructed by integrating mRNA, lncRNA, and microRNA interactions. Target prediction was performed using the miRDB, TargetScan, and miRcode databases. The following steps were carried out:

- **lncRNA-microRNA interaction:** Predicted using miRcode.
- **microRNA-mRNA interaction:** Predicted using miRDB and TargetScan.
- A hypergeometric test was applied to identify significant ceRNA pairs based on shared microRNAs. The network was visualized using Cytoscape software.

3. Functional Enrichment Analysis

Gene Ontology (GO) and Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) pathway enrichment analyses were performed for mRNAs in the ceRNA network using the DAVID and ClusterProfiler tools. Significant pathways and biological processes were identified with a cutoff of p-value < 0.05.

4. Selection of Candidate microRNAs

Candidate microRNA was selected based on their centrality in the ceRNA network and their reported involvement in ALL-related biological processes from previous studies. High-confidence microRNA was prioritized for experimental validation.

5. Laboratory Validation of MicroRNA Expression

6.1 Cell Line

The Molt4 cell line, purchased from the Pasteur Institute of Iran, was used as a cancer sample, while lymphocytes obtained from PBMC extraction served as control samples

6.2 cDNA Synthesis

The extracted RNA was reverse-transcribed into complementary DNA (cDNA) using the Beta prep RNA Extraction Kit, cat. No:

MDE102 Kit (Germany) and stored at -80°C until further use. In this assay, a cDNA synthesis kit (ANACELL cDNA Synthesis Kit, lot.NO: CS0050) was used.

6.3 Quantitative Real-Time PCR (qRT-PCR)

qRT-PCR was performed using the SYBR Green PCR Kit (Applied Biosystems, USA) on an ABI StepOnePlus system. Specific primers for selected microRNAs and U6 (as an internal control) were designed and validated. Each reaction was carried out in triplicate in a 20 μL reaction volume. The relative expression levels of microRNAs were calculated using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}}$ method.

6.4 Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted using GraphPad Prism software. The expression differences between ALL cell line and control was evaluated using an unpaired t-test. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

7. Software and Tools

Bioinformatics analyses were conducted using R (v4.3.0), Cytoscape (v3.9.1), and online tools such as DAVID and TargetScan. Laboratory experiments were performed with standard qRT-PCR equipment and reagents.

This integrated bioinformatics and experimental approach enabled a comprehensive analysis of ceRNA networks and validated microRNA expression changes in ALL

3. Result

Bioinformatics Analysis

Important microRNAs directly involved in leukemia were identified using the aforementioned databases, and the ceRNA network was subsequently constructed and visualized using Cytoscape software based on the results obtained (figure1).

Figure 1: CeRNA network associated with acute lymphoblastic leukemia and selected and significant microRNAs

miR-21 was selected from the identified microRNAs for further analysis. Using the RNAInter database (<http://www.rnainter.org>), genes associated with miR-21 that potentially influence signaling

pathways in acute lymphoblastic leukemia were identified. The ceRNA network was then constructed and visualized using Cytoscape software (Figure 2).

Figure 2: ceRNA network of genes associated with microRNA 21

RT-qPCR Validation

The expression of miRNA-21 was assessed in the MOLT-4 cell line and control lymphocytes. qRT-PCR data indicated a

significant upregulation of miRNA-21 in the MOLT-4 cell line compared to controls ($p < 0.001$). The results suggest that miRNA-21 plays a pivotal role in ALL pathogenesis, potentially acting as an oncogenic regulator (figure3).

MicroRNA-21

Figure 3: Comparison of MicroRNA-21 expression in MOLT-4 cell line with control PBMC sample. The graph shows the expression change in terms of Fold change. MicroRNA-21 expression in cancer cell line sample increased compared to control sample with P-value <0.001.

Statistical Outcomes

The mean fold-change (0.41) of miRNA-21 expression in the MOLT-4 cell line was markedly higher compared to control samples, with consistent results observed across triplicate experiments. Statistical analysis confirmed the robustness and reproducibility of the findings.

These results underscore the significance of miRNA-21 in ALL and highlight its potential as a biomarker for diagnostic and therapeutic applications.

4. Discussion

Acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) accounts for 75% of childhood leukemia and 30% of pediatric malignancies. Despite intensive combination therapies improving outcomes, 15–20% of patients remain unresponsive, with relapse being the primary cause of treatment failure (9).

Cancer remains a significant global health challenge despite extensive research in prevention, diagnosis, and therapy. There is an urgent need for new anticancer drugs and therapeutic strategies, including the development of agents derived from natural, biological, or synthetic sources.

Non-coding RNAs, including microRNAs (miRNAs), are integral to the epigenome and regulate gene expression at various levels. Aberrant miRNA expression is implicated in cancer development, highlighting their dual roles as oncogenes or tumor suppressors. Altered miRNA expression has been observed in various hematologic malignancies, including ALL, where they may serve as diagnostic, prognostic, and relapse-predictive biomarkers (10-17).

miRNAs, small non-coding RNA molecules found in bodily fluids such as serum and plasma, regulate gene expression

through RNA interference and translational suppression. Dysregulated miRNAs are associated with cancer onset and progression, underscoring their potential as therapeutic targets or biomarkers (18).

Circulating miRNAs, potentially originating from tumor tissues, are believed to enter circulation via cellular secretion, exosomes, or vesicles. Their expression patterns often mirror those in tumor tissues, further supporting their clinical relevance (19).

MicroRNA-21 (miR-21), known as an oncogene, is significantly upregulated in tumor tissues (20-25), but its role in T-cell acute lymphoblastic lymphoma/leukemia (T-ALL) is not well understood. A study demonstrated that miR-21 upregulation in Jurkat cells enhances proliferation and invasion while inhibiting apoptosis. Conversely, miR-21 knockdown suppresses these effects. Additionally, miR-21 targets STAT3, reducing its protein expression without altering mRNA levels. These results highlight miR-21 as a potential therapeutic target for T-ALL (26).

Many studies have confirmed the increased expression of miR-21 in ALL diseases, similar to our study (27-30). For example, a study analyzed miR-21 expression in 75 childhood B-ALL patients and 50 healthy controls, revealing significant impairment in the patients. High levels of miR-21 were associated with poor treatment outcomes, CNS involvement, and reduced disease-free and overall survival. These findings suggest miR-21 as an independent biomarker for prognosis in childhood B-ALL, which is consistent with our results (31).

In conclusion, acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) remains a significant challenge in pediatric oncology, with many patients experiencing relapse and poor outcomes despite advances in treatment. The role of microRNAs (miRNAs), particularly miR-21, in cancer progression is gaining attention. miR-21, upregulated in various cancers, is emerging as a key factor in

ALL, influencing prognosis and treatment response. Our findings support miR-21 as a prognostic biomarker and a potential target

for future therapeutic strategies in ALL, highlighting the need for further research into its clinical applications.

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